

NEAR ULTRASONIC ATTACK AND DEFENSIVE COUNTERMEASURES

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ABSTRACT

The practical implications of issuing inaudible voice commands. The research mapped each attack vector to a tactic or technique from the MITRE ATT&CK matrix, covering enterprise, mobile, and Industrial Control System (ICS) frameworks. The experiment involved generating and surveying fifty near-ultrasonic audios to assess the attacks' effectiveness. Unprocessed commands achieved a 100% success rate, while processed commands achieved an 86% acknowledgment rate and a 58% overall executed (successful) rate. The research systematically stimulated previously unaddressed attack surfaces, aiming for comprehensive detection and attack design. Each ATT&CK identifier was paired with a tested defensive method, providing attack and defense tactics. The research findings revealed that the attack method employed Single Upper Sideband Amplitude Modulation (SUSBAM) to generate near-ultrasonic audio from audible sources. By eliminating the lower sideband, the design achieved a 6 kHz minimum from 16-22 kHz while remaining inaudible after transformation. The research also investigated the one-to-many attack surface, exploring scenarios where a single device triggers multiple actions or devices. Furthermore, the study demonstrated the reversibility or demodulation of the inaudible signal, suggesting potential alerting methods and the possibility of embedding secret messages like audio steganography. A critical methodological advance included tapping into the post-processed audio signal when the server demodulates the signal for comparison to both the audible and inaudible input signals to improve the actionable success rates.

KEYWORDS

Cybersecurity, voice activation, digital signal processing, Internet of Things, ultrasonic audio

1. INTRODUCTION

The present research examines high-frequency inaudible commands that affect network behavior. These novel attack surfaces open a gate way to significant financial, health, and personal information that may remain undetected for alerts and long monitoring periods. We explore this attack surface using inaudible commands (Figure 1). The work investigates the potential effects and vulnerabilities of near-ultrasonic attacks on voice-activated devices and seeks to identify possible countermeasures [1-45]. The research focuses on mapping inaudible commands to consequential cases for cybersecurity when combined with digital signal-processing techniques [38-56].

Figure 1. Example inaudible signal from a smartphone broadcast to a home device receiver

Voice-controlled systems and digital voice assistants have witnessed a significant surge in popularity and adoption in recent years [1, 2]. However, the convenience and ubiquity of these technologies have also raised concerns about their security and vulnerability to cyber-attacks. Voice-activated devices have become increasingly prevalent daily, with billions of digital voice assistants worldwide and a significant market share held by popular platforms such as Apple Siri, Google Assistant, and Amazon Alexa [1-2]. Researchers have made progress in developing defense mechanisms and detection techniques to counter ultrasonic attacks and other security risks associated with voice-activated devices [3-17]. Continued vigilance and innovation are essential to ensuring user safety and privacy [14].

Figure 2. Printed Circuit Board (PCB 1) from Echo Dot Generation 2 Teardown Highlights the Analog-Digital Interfaces

Open microphones in private and public spaces raise security concerns, as access to these devices can potentially provide deep access to personal and sensitive information [19, 28-49]. Wake words are typically used to activate the microphones, but no additional security or identifier is often required to access the device's functionalities [20, 22-24]. Researchers have demonstrated the potential for exploiting surrounding microphones to perform complex tasks without user input or knowledge [19, 33-49]. Unauthorized access to voice-activated devices can have real-world consequences, from manipulating home automation systems to compromising personally identifiable information and financial accounts [50-59]. The attack surface of audio vulnerabilities is extensive, encompassing various devices, their types, and typical locations in homes and other environments [19, 64-70]. In addition to offensive cyber risks, researchers have also investigated using audio steganography, covert channels, air-gap computer trojans, jammers, and firewalls to address these security challenges [69, 73-74, 76, 77].

A growing body of research has focused on exploring the security challenges and potential risks associated with voice assistants, paving the way for developing robust defenses and countermeasures. Previous studies conducted in voice assistant security encompass various clusters of topics, including unconventional cyber-attacks, security and privacy challenges, specific attack scenarios, practical attacks, and countermeasures, and comprehensive surveys and analyses.

A critical aspect of research in this field has been investigating unconventional cyber attacks targeting voice-controlled systems [3, 17, 28, 34, 43, 47]. These studies have shed light on voice assistants' vulnerabilities and potential threats, emphasizing the need for comprehensive security measures. By identifying attack vectors and examining the practical implications of these attacks, researchers have aimed to uncover potential attack surfaces and enhance detection and defense mechanisms.

Another cluster of research has centered around the security and privacy challenges inherent in voice assistants and smart home devices [4, 7, 14, 21, 25, 27, 31, 32, 36, 40, 44, 48, 52, 58, 59, 62, 63, 66, 67, 68, 71, 74, 78, 79, 80, 81]. These studies have explored various attack techniques, vulnerabilities, and defense mechanisms, aiming to establish a comprehensive understanding of the risks associated with these technologies. By addressing issues such as unauthorized access, data leakage, and privacy concerns, researchers have strived to create a secure environment for voice-controlled systems.

Pioneering work on the Near Ultrasonic Inaudible Trojan (NUIT) has showcased the vulnerabilities of voice-activated devices [19]. NUIT exploits microphone nonlinearities and can execute attacks without special hardware. The proximity between the device and the target plays a crucial role in the success of these attacks [19]. Further research is expected to explore one-to-many attacks and their potential to penetrate larger populations of devices [19] simultaneously.

Specific attack scenarios have also been the focus of previous investigations, highlighting the potential for hidden voice commands, audio adversarial examples, and covert channels [5, 12, 15, 22, 23, 26, 30, 35, 39, 41, 42, 45, 51, 54, 55, 56, 60, 61, 64, 69, 73, 75]. These studies have examined the feasibility and implications of these attack techniques, aiming to develop effective detection and mitigation strategies. By exploring the manipulation of inaudible signals, the exploitation of vulnerabilities in voice recognition systems, and the challenges posed by acoustic attacks, researchers have sought to unveil the potential risks and devise effective countermeasures.

Practical attacks and countermeasures have also been a subject of research interest, focusing on the development of selective ultrasonic microphone jammers, defense schemes against specific attacks, and threat modeling [6, 9, 18, 24, 33, 38, 46, 49, 50, 53, 57, 65, 70, 76, 77, 82]. These studies have aimed to provide practical solutions to protect voice assistants and mitigate potential risks. By developing resilient evaluation frameworks, exploring defense mechanisms against specific attack vectors, and analyzing the security of voice-controlled systems, researchers have strived to enhance the overall security posture of these technologies.

Surveys, analyses, and investigations into specific aspects of voice assistant security have also contributed significantly to the field [8, 10, 11, 13, 16, 20, 29, 37, 39, 50, 69, 72, 83]. These studies have provided comprehensive insights into the attack surface, vulnerabilities, and potential mitigations, allowing for a deeper understanding of the security challenges posed by voice-controlled systems. By examining the prevalence of attacks, the feasibility of injecting inaudible voice commands, and the potential impact on user privacy, researchers have paved the way for informed decision-making and effective security strategies.

Various defense techniques have been proposed to counteract the threat of ultrasonic attacks. One approach involves using the physical fingerprinting of ultrasonic sensors to enhance their security [68], while another defense focuses on canceling inaudible voice commands against voice control systems [8]. For instance, an Ear Array [41] defends against Dolphin Attacks through acoustic attenuation. These defense mechanisms protect voice-activated devices from malicious ultrasonic interference [55]. In addition to defense mechanisms, researchers have developed techniques to detect ultrasonic attacks. Watchdog, a system proposed in one study [60], is designed to detect ultrasonic-based inaudible voice attacks on smart-home systems. Another detection method, FOCUS [74], is frequency-based and aims to identify covert ultrasonic signals in ICT (Information Control Systems). These detection techniques attempt to counter unauthorized access to voice-activated devices.

Table 1 summarizes cross-device examples of open microphones that listen perpetually for the next instruction and second-order skills that enable complex tasks to commence from the “wake word” and command sequence.

Table 1. Cross-device networked attacks by study references

Source/Target	iPhone	Alexa	Cortana	Android	YouTube	Home
iPhone	[19,21,32]	[10,19,44]	[19]	[19]	[19]	[19,28]
Alexa	[19,21]	[10,19,44]	[10,19,44]	[10,19,44]		[19,28]
Cortana	[19,21]	[10,19,44]	[19,31]			[19,28]
Android	[19,21]	[10,19,44]		[19]		[19,28]
YouTube	[19,21]	[10,19, 44]			[19]	[19,28]
Home						[19,28]

Despite the advancements in defense and detection techniques, new attack vectors continue to emerge [10,19,44]. For example, the Near-Ultrasonic Covert Channels method utilizes software-defined radio techniques to create covert channels for transmitting data [69]. Similarly, the HVAC attack method evades classifier-based defenses in hidden voice attacks [13]. Ultrasonic attacks are not limited to voice-activated devices; they also target other systems, such as vehicular sensors [61-62, 64] and autonomous vehicles [62]. These researchers highlight the broader impact of ultrasonic

attacks on various connected systems, particularly when the attack couples to a device capable of performing many dangerous downstream commands or executing voice-activated skills [28].

Figure 3. Printed Circuit Board (PCB 2) on Echo Dot 2 Highlights the Sensory Inputs for Voice and Touch Commands

As shown in Figure 4, the present work explores a primary inaudible attack vector using Amazon Alexa voice services as the target and multiple input devices to deliver near-ultrasound trojans [19]. In contrast to previous approaches, the research explores the attack surface of one target device rather than surveying the large search space of voice-activated device combinations. The interest centers on characterizing the attack surface and exploring the practical implications of issuing inaudible voice commands to the Amazon Alexa system in various contexts and connected states.

Figure 4. SUSBAM signal in time and frequency domains

We use the MITRE ATT&CK matrix [78-81] to systematically address the problem to map each attack vector to an existing tactic or technique. The voice-activation element can be found in various devices, including enterprise (Cortana), mobile (Android, iPhone), home, and Internet of Things (IoT) devices (Alexa, Google), resulting in overlapping attack vectors across different frameworks. To accommodate this, the MITRE ATT&CK framework incorporates notation for enterprise, mobile, and Industrial Control System (ICS) environments [82]. This systematic approach offers two key advantages. Firstly, it enables the exploration of previously unaddressed attack surfaces by leveraging knowledge from the broader cybersecurity domain beyond voice activation. A framework

ensures comprehensive coverage for detecting and designing new attacks. Secondly, it facilitates the pairing of each ATT&CK Identifier with at least one tested defensive method. The MITRE frameworks provide both red team tactics (attack) and blue team tactics (defender) as prompt-response options [82]. By combining these advantages, our approach promotes a thorough understanding of potential threats and enables the development of effective defense strategies.

2. METHODS

As first reported [19], the attack generates near-ultrasonic audio from audible sources using Single Upper Sideband Amplitude Modulation (SUSBAM). As illustrated in time and frequency space (Figure 5), the method transforms a spoken command to a voice-activated device using the modulated audio signal converted into a frequency range (16-22 kHz) beyond human-adult hearing. Stepwise, the method applies a low-pass filter with a cutoff of 6 kHz to the original spoken signal and removes components not essential to the SUSBAM generation. The generator normalizes the remaining audio signal and applies a carrier frequency (16 kHz) to shift the audible range of the input signal to a higher frequency (near ultrasonic, 16-22 kHz). Figure 4 shows the original and transformed signal as an example in waveform (time domain) and spectral (frequency and power density domain). Figure 5 overlays the audible and inaudible signals as spectrograms.

To modulate the voice command, a 90-degree phase-shifted version gets created from a Hilbert-transformed input, then modulated as a combination of the original signal, its Hilbert-transformed version, and the assigned carrier frequency. To taper the signal's edges to zero smoothly, a Tukey window is applied to the modulated signal, which reduces spectral leakage in the frequency domain and prevents artifacts in the near-ultrasonic output. The method normalizes the SUSBAM signal to a 16-bit integer PCM audio format range, then casts the normalized SUSBAM signal to the int16 data type expected from an uncompressed WAV file. Compression in later stages of SUSBAM generation to MP3 formats loses functionality. In summary, the NUIT process reads an input audio signal, applies a low-pass filter, modulates the signal using SUSBAM to shift it to a near-ultrasonic frequency range, applies a Tukey window, normalizes, converts the signal to an integer format, and writes the processed signal to an output WAV file.

Figure 5. Original (middle) and transformed (lower and upper) signals in time and frequency domains

2.1. Approach to Exploring the Command Attack Surface

The MITRE framework represents a catalog for examining the available attack and defending surfaces for the near-ultrasound vectors. The Appendix outlines example stages grouped by tactics such as initial access, then the various techniques used in the literature. The most apparent result of an inaudible attack on voice-activated devices follows initial access using a drive-by compromise (Table 2). The attacker does not need keyboard availability (either locally or remotely) at the time of the initial entry. The attacker can access a set command list either innately or through additional applications (called "skills" in Alexa). A remote attacker may embed the vector in the silence of an online video (YouTube) that is currently popular or "going viral," then gain both a distribution "worm-like" quality along with accessing what is, in practice, a password-less means to discover financial, health, personal or other damaging information about the victim. The recommended MITRE defense for the attack is user training, which in this case might specialize to the position of the Echo device in a space accessible to the attacker or include specific profile configurations that limit what an unrecognized voice can accomplish.

Similarly, an attacker may use an ultrasonic attack to target valid accounts by employing ultrasonic signals to inject a malicious skill onto a target device, replacing an existing skill [82]. This tactic allows the attacker to prompt the user to enter or re-enter personal information, facilitating input capture. Upon successfully capturing the desired information, the attacker can then use it to access a valid account, which may have elevated privileges, enabling the attacker to move laterally within the target network. The recommended MITRE defense for the attack would be User Training and Access control. In practice, this could be to have a user verify a skill is genuine and to allow users to have the minimum privilege needed.

Appendix A shows the plausible mapping of these attacks to known stages of the MITRE framework, along with paired defenses. A notable aspect of this map suggests new avenues that have not appeared in previous broad surveys meant to explore the various device and microphone combinations. Given the right skills, connectivity, and access, this work centers on the deeper attack surfaces available on one device.

Table 2. Example Near Ultrasonic Attack and the Paired Defend Tactics and Techniques

ATT&CK Tactic	ATT&CK Technique	D3FEND Tactic	D3FEND Technique	Ultrasonic Attack
Initial Access	T1189: Drive-by Compromise	User Training	D3-T1023: Security Awareness Training	Yes
Privilege Escalation	T1078: Valid Accounts	Access Control	D3-T1021: User Account Management	Yes
Credential Access	T1056: Input Capture	User Training	D3-T1023: Security Awareness Training	Yes

2.2. Approach to Exploring the Command Response Surface

Amazon devices record the transmitted messages on their server, which offers interpretable feedback from the transmitted inaudible signal, the demodulated microphone (IoT device), and finally, the actionable interpretation on the host (Amazon server [85]). This "Review Voice History" provides a paired record for every issued inaudible command, but as the server receives it post-processed into

the audible range. We examined the feedback to compare commands that worked against those that did not either acknowledge or generate the requested command. An essential step in understanding the inaudible-to-audible translation further relies on sending known sinusoidal (single) frequencies and comparing those to the theoretical [19] and actual microphone responses.

2.3. Approach to Examining Text-to-Speech Engines

Text-to-Speech (TTS) has the advantage of being quickly generated at a large scale. TTS offers an experimental platform for testing NUIT commands as reproducible inputs, thus limiting any errors due to fluctuations in command delivery from the human voice. The research explored multiple candidates for TTS in trial-and-error experiments but ultimately selected the gTTS library. We did not initially find a significant effect for different voice synthesizers based on the age or gender of the TTS avatar. Future opportunities for TTS engines offer higher sample rates and more advanced generation techniques to aid Voice Control System (VCS) detection. Different gendered voices, accents, speed, pitch, and volume are all potential avenues to explore to increase NUIT reliability.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Survey Test of Voice-Activated Commands

Figure 6. NUIT2 Attacks from Android to Echo Dot Gen 2/3 Devices: "Alexa, what's the weather?"

Table 3 shows the success rate with unprocessed TTS commands and transformed TTS commands. The experiment included fifty orders to survey the attacks' effectiveness based on a repeatable text-to-speech generated input modified by the modulation algorithm. The unprocessed commands had a 100% success rate, while the processed ones had a success rate of 58%. 26% of the audio recordings got Alexa to acknowledge the command, but the device's microphone failed to recognize the wake word or follow the order. Alexa failed to trigger the final 16%. Figure 6 shows a two-panel image of an Android (S9 model) playing the "What's the weather?" attack on both Amazon Alexa Echo Dot Generation 2/3 devices. These attack vectors would qualify as NUIT2 [19], signifying that there is a two-device audible connection, one from the broadcaster (phone) to a receiver (home device).

More research is needed to diagnose why some commands had higher success than others, but a simple explanation would be that the VCS more easily understands some combinations of syllables from the TTS service than others. When these command-specific variables combine with the

exploited nonlinearity in the VCS microphone may account for the lower success rates of the VCS algorithms.

Table 3. Survey of Actionable Commands in the Voice-Activated Device and Success Rates for Recognition and Response as Actions

ID	Command	Original (mp3)			Near Ultrasound (NUIT)		
		fail	trigger	success	fail	trigger	success
0	Help			x			x
1	Mute			x	x		
2	Unmute			x			x
3	Stop			x		x	
4	Louder			x			x
5	Set the volume to five			x		x	
6	Play some music			x			x
7	Set a timer for one minute			x			x
8	What's playing?			x			x
9	When is Christmas next year?			x			x
10	What's on my calendar for tomorrow?			x			x
11	What's in the news?			x			x
12	What's the weather like?			x			x
13	What's the traffic like?			x			x
14	What movies are playing?			x			x
15	What is Tom Holland's latest movie?			x	x		
16	Who is in The Rolling Stones?			x			x
17	What's five plus seven?			x			x
18	Flip a coin			x			x
19	Pick a number between one and ten			x			x
20	What's the definition of ultrasound?			x			x
21	How do you spell Apple?			x			x
22	Did the Lakers win?			x		x wrong cmd	
23	When do the Lakers play next?			x			x
24	Which profile is this?			x	x		
25	What kid's skills do you have?			x			x
26	Wikipedia ultrasound			x			x
27	How tall is Steph Curry?			x	x		
28	Tell me a joke			x			x

ID	Command	Original (mp3)			Near Ultrasound (NUIT)		
29	Beam me up			x			x
30	Set phasers to kill			x		x	
31	Tea. Earl grey. Hot.			x		x	
32	My name is Inigo Montoya			x			x
33	I want the truth			x	x		
34	Party on, Wayne.			x		x wrong cmd	
35	Show me the money!			x			x
36	What's the first rule of Fight Club?			x			x
37	Surely you can't be serious			x		x	
38	Are you Skynet?			x		x	
39	Party time!			x		x wrong cmd	
40	Open the pod bay doors.			x			x
41	What is your quest?			x		x wrong cmd	
42	Don't mention the war			x	x		
43	What is your cunning plan?			x		x wrong cmd	
44	What is the loneliest number?			x		x	
45	What is the best tablet?			x	x		
46	Do aliens exist?			x		x	
47	Where do you live?			x	x		
48	How tall are you?			x			x
49	I think you're funny			x			x
	Total	0	0	50	8	13	29
	%	0	0	1	0.16	0.26	0.58

A critical element of the NUIT design follows from eliminating the lower sideband to achieving a 6 kHz minimum from 16-22 kHz while remaining inaudible after transformation. In other words, the selective removal of modulated elements that might leak provides the spectral room to span the minimum detection needs of the non-linear microphone interactions. Figure 6 shows a two-device attack surface (NUIT2) with the broadcaster (Android) near the receiver (Alexa Echo) in two different models [86]. The inaudible WAV file plays four times ("Alexa, what's the weather?"), and the blue ring on the target device signifies the two stages of acknowledgment (signal recognition) and the intended action (comprehension and result).

3.2. Extensible Attack Surfaces: NUIT-N Design

To extend the previous single and dual-device attacks [19], we outline a one-to-many design common to many public events where an audible broadcast might embed an inaudible command within the silence and effectively trigger an entire crowd. Examples include a public announcer (PA system), a live online broadcast (YouTube or Facebook live), a concert hall, or a network of home devices (Alexa groups). This version extends the one-device and two-device attack surface to any number we subsequently call NUIT-N (Near Ultrasonic Inaudible Trojan-N). We demonstrate this phenomenon in a straightforward setup as one broadcasting device (phone) that inaudibly controls multiple home devices simultaneously. In Figure 7, the NUIT signal sends "Alexa, what's the weather?" to both devices inaudibly, thus fulfilling the (N) requirement at a basic level. Video demonstration replays are available online [84].

Figure 7. NUIT-N Attack Linking a Single Broadcasting Device to Multiple Receivers Simultaneously

3.3. Demodulation

Running the demodulation algorithm on the attack signal captured by an inexpensive microphone reveals reversibility in ambient noise (Figure 8). The slight degradation in the signal quality appears in both the spectrogram and waveform representations of the signal. The spectrogram shows that the demodulation recovers energy around 3kHz, while the digital signal recovers roughly 6kHz (Figure 8). Aside from the ambient noise, a potential factor for the loss in signal quality is the speaker and microphone's frequency response.

Running the demodulation algorithm on the digital variant of the attack signal reveals near-perfect recovery. The waveform of the demodulated signal captured by an inexpensive microphone indicates a periodic signal underneath various spikes in amplitude representing the original voice signal. Demodulating the digital signal reveals the upper portion of the envelope of the Tukey Window (Figure 8D).

3.4. Monitoring the Server Translation from Inaudible to Audible Commands

The Amazon Voice History feature [85] gives an automated log for debugging the "prompt-response" sequences for the commands that work (or do not) using the near ultrasonic transformation. On the server, the voice profile of the speaker may also connect to the demodulated version received from the remote device. The voice history reflects a guessed identity assignment if the user configures voice profiles during setup. In the present cases, the text-to-speech element rendered this assignment moot, except for server guesses for the gender and age of the speaker. Figure 9 shows the four main stages of signal generation, near ultrasonic transformation, demodulation, and actionable server recording in one view. While not identical, the resulting output recovers sufficient signal from the non-linear aspects of the microphone to transmit an audible command at a lower frequency. The figure shows both the wake words ("Alexa") and command sequences in time (waveform) and frequency (spectrogram). The waveforms mainly show the distinct pauses needed for reconstructing the commanded speech as an Alexa response or skill.

Figure 8. Recovery of Inaudible Signal Aids Defensive Detection of Command Intention

4. DISCUSSION

The main results show that the attack method generates near-ultrasonic audio from audible sources using SUSBAM. In other words, the selective removal of modulated elements that might leak provides the spectral room to span the minimum detection needs of the non-linear microphone interactions. We demonstrate reversibility or demodulation of the inaudible signal to highlight future alerting methods and show that an attacker may embed secret (or subliminal) messages like audio steganography.

Several stages of SUSBAM might hinder its usefulness for microphone detection if compression, speed, pitch, or amplitude are incorrect. Proper compression, speed, pitch, and amplitude handling are crucial for generating near-ultrasonic audio that microphones can accurately detect and demodulate. Factors such as the low-pass filter, normalization, carrier frequency, SUSBAM modulation, and Tukey window can significantly affect the effectiveness of the near-ultrasonic audio transmission if not configured correctly. If the cutoff frequency is set too low, important frequency components might be filtered out, affecting the pitch and intelligibility of the signal. This lower cutoff might make it difficult for microphones to detect and recognize the original audio content. The normalization stage scales the signal to have a maximum amplitude of 1. If the original signal has a very low amplitude, the normalization could amplify noise and other undesired components, which might negatively affect microphone detection.

The choice of the carrier frequency (16 kHz in this example) is crucial for shifting the signal into the near-ultrasonic range. If the carrier frequency is too low, the modulated signal might still be within the audible range, causing interference with other sounds and reducing the effectiveness of the near-ultrasonic audio transmission. On the other hand, if the carrier frequency is too high, some microphones might not detect the modulated signal, as a low pass filter is generally employed to filter out frequencies greater than the human audible range (such as 20kHz).

If the input signal's amplitude or pitch is unsuitable for the chosen modulation scheme, the resulting modulated signal might be complex for microphones to detect or demodulate accurately. In addition, if the speed or pitch of the input signal is significantly altered before SUSBAM modulation, it might affect the modulated signal's ability to be accurately demodulated and recognized.

The Tukey window is applied to reduce spectral leakage and prevent artifacts in the audio signal. However, if the window's alpha parameter is not chosen correctly, it might cause undesirable effects on the signal, such as attenuating important frequency components or altering the pitch, which could hinder microphone detection.

Figure 9. Waveform and spectrograms show the major attack stages in time and frequency domains

Several advanced attack scenarios seem plausible, given that an attacker embeds the inaudible commands into silent periods of a well-attended public event. Previous work [19] has considered the potentially viral capabilities to embed NUIT signals in YouTube videos. Following the basic MITRE steps to propagate a denial-of-service or self-propagating worm attack, one can consider future defensive actions. For example, an attacker could take stealth control of a public announcer system at a stadium or Grand Central Station to broadcast an inaudible trigger during a silent part, potentially

reaching a large audience and their devices simultaneously. In both scenarios, the PA broadcasts an inaudible trigger to a large audience during a quiet part of the broadcast. To accomplish a NUIT attack, the attacker and defenders might address the following steps proactively, as described in Table 4.

Table 4. NUIT-N Scenario Development for One-to-Many Attack and Defend Cycles

Stage	Attack Description	Plausible Defenses or Limits
Prepare the inaudible trigger	Utilize the SUSBAM technique or a similar method to create an inaudible audio command that triggers the desired response in the targeted devices. Ensure that the modulated signal is in the near-ultrasonic frequency range (e.g., 16-22 kHz) to avoid audible disturbances to the audience.	Advanced preparations may be needed, including intercepting a public announcer system control. Children under 14 may hear the annoying signal inaudible to those older in a mixed audience.
PA system setup	For the stadium scenario, install a high-quality public address system with speakers strategically placed throughout the venue to ensure even coverage. The design should be capable of accurately reproducing the inaudible trigger signal at a sufficient volume level. In the case of Grand Central Station, the PA system should be adapted to the train departure areas to ensure that the signal reaches all targeted devices.	The microphone-broadcast pairing appears as less than 60% reliable in initial trials. Event planning suggests a high risk for detection and a lower risk for success.
Signal synchronization	To effectively broadcast the inaudible trigger, ensure proper synchronization of the PA system. Synchrony will help maintain signal integrity and prevent potential interference or audible artifacts during the silent part of the broadcast.	Previous batch modification of audio signals (using MATLAB or other advanced platforms) may not mix well with live streams.
Timing	Choose the appropriate timing for broadcasting the inaudible trigger, such as during a moment of silence at the stadium or a brief pause between train departure announcements at Grand Central Station. Timing control will increase the chances of the targeted devices receiving the signal without interference from other noises.	If conceived as a prank or denial of service, the effects are, at best temporary. The introduction of remote control of home devices such as locks or cameras may suggest consequential losses for those away from home but triggered by device attacks
Testing	Before broadcasting the inaudible trigger to the public, conduct tests in a controlled environment to ensure that the PA system can accurately reproduce the signal and that the targeted devices can detect and respond to it as intended	Validation and verification seem challenging before live events and inadequate trial attempts. Background noise and weather conditions may limit confidence even with tests.

For securing devices, themselves, potential countermeasures at the user level could include acoustic shielding, frequency fingerprinting, user voice authentication, and device-level security updates, as summarized in Table 5.

Future work will explore the device combinations and underlying non-linear physics associated with the device's particular broadcaster and receiver in tandem. Some limitations of the SUSBAM attack include the proximity requirement of the attacking device and the spatial requirement of the receiving device, which involves the geometry of the acoustical setting without deflecting ultrasonic wave surfaces. Additionally, specific speaker dependencies or biometrics, such as Siri voice print and Alexa profile for understanding household voices, may not entirely halt the attack but can act as a

filter for specific dangerous commands. Finally, proper signal pre-processing is necessary to avoid audible leakage, as NUIT [19] suggests only babies can hear above 20 kHz. However, in some experiments, children under 14 were disturbed by the high-frequency attack, indicating the importance of addressing audible leakage even at 16 kHz thresholds.

Table 5. Survey of Defensive Tactics to Detect Attacks and Protect Voice-Activated Devices

Defensive tactic	Description
Acoustic shielding	Designing devices with materials that dampen or reflect ultrasonic signals, reducing their impact on the device's microphone
Frequency filtering	Implementing digital filters to remove ultrasonic frequencies from the audio input, preventing the device from processing inaudible commands
Machine learning	Employing machine learning algorithms to identify and block unauthorized ultrasonic signals based on their unique characteristics
User authentication	Requiring user authentication before executing sensitive actions, thereby reducing the risk of unauthorized access or control
Device-level security updates	Ensuring that device manufacturers provide timely security updates and patches to address newly discovered vulnerabilities

5. CONCLUSIONS

Voice-activated devices pose a significant security challenge due to vulnerabilities in both hardware and software. One emerging threat is the Near Ultrasound Inaudible Trojan (NUIT), named after the French word for "night." NUIT encompasses two versions: Version 1, which targets a single device, and Version 2, which involves two devices. These attacks exploit the nonlinearities of microphones and can be executed without the need for specialized hardware.

Additionally, the Near Ultrasound Attack on Networked Communication Environments (NUANCE) highlights the connectivity aspect of attacks. NUANCE expands the attack surface by targeting multiple networked devices with escalating skills. This approach increases the complexity and potential impact of the attacks. Understanding these various versions and the escalating skill in NUANCE is essential for developing effective defense strategies and mitigating the risks associated with voice-activated devices.

As this paper has shown, near ultrasonic attacks can seriously threaten these devices' security. As IoT technology continues to evolve, security researchers and practitioners must remain vigilant in identifying and mitigating emerging threats, such as near ultrasonic attacks, to ensure the safety and privacy of IoT users. These findings replicate previous results that ultrasonic attacks on voice-activated devices represent a viable threat with many potential consequences and extend previous work to include the MITRE security frameworks. We extend the attack surface to consider NUIT-N configurations where an attacking device simultaneously gains control over many (N) devices. The susceptibility of these devices to inaudible signals highlights the importance of developing countermeasures to protect users' authentication, privacy, and security.

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Appendix A: Example Stages of MITRE Tactic and Technique Classifications in both Attack and Defend Cycles with Reference to Viable Near Ultrasonic Methods

ATT&CK Tactic	ATT&CK Technique	D3FEND Tactic	D3FEND Technique	Ultrasonic Attack
Initial Access	T1189: Drive-by Compromise	User Training	D3-T1023: Security Awareness Training	Yes
	T1200: Hardware Additions	Physical Security	D3-T1042: Physical Access Control	Yes
Execution	T1204: User Execution	User Training	D3-T1023: Security Awareness Training	Yes
	T1129: Execution through Module Load	Application Control	D3-T1008: Application Whitelisting	Yes
Persistence	T1060: Registry Run Keys / Startup Folder	System Hardening	D3-T1035: Security Policy Enforcement	Yes
	T1166: Setuid and Setgid	System Hardening	D3-T1005: Privilege Management	Yes
Privilege Escalation	T1078: Valid Accounts	Access Control	D3-T1021: User Account Management	Yes
	T1134: Access Token Manipulation	System Hardening	D3-T1005: Privilege Management	Yes
Defense Evasion	T1140: Deobfuscate/Decode Files or Information	Malware Protection	D3-T1009: Anti-Malware Deployment	Yes
	T1158: Hidden Files and Directories	Logging & Monitoring	D3-T1016: Log Management	Yes
Credential Access	T1056: Input Capture	User Training	D3-T1023: Security Awareness Training	Yes
	T1110: Brute Force	Account Lockout Policy	D3-T1022: Account Lockout Policy Implementation	Yes
Lateral Movement	T1021: Remote Services	Access Control	D3-T1021: Service Account Management	Yes
	T1028: Windows Remote Management	Network Segmentation	D3-T1041: Network Segmentation	Yes
Collection	T1113: Screen Capture	User Training	D3-T1023: Security Awareness Training	Yes
	T1119: Automated Collection	Data Loss Prevention	D3-T1010: Data Classification	Yes
Command and Control	T1043: Commonly Used Port	Network Segmentation	D3-T1041: Network Segmentation	Yes
	T1573: Encrypted Channel	Network Monitoring	D3-T1017: Network Traffic Analysis	Yes
Exfiltration	T1041: Exfiltration Over Command and Control Channel	Data Loss Prevention	D3-T1010: Data Classification	Yes
	T1567: Exfiltration Over Web Service	Network Monitoring	D3-T1017: Network Traffic Analysis	Yes